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1. Executive Summary

On October 19, 2023, ESNA - Europe Startup Nations Alliance successfully convened its third annual ESNA Forum in León, Spain, in collaboration with its Spanish associate member, INCIBE, the Spanish National Cybersecurity Institute. This international conference, held under the patronage of the Spanish Presidency of the Council of the EU, marked a significant gathering of ESNA's member and signatory countries of the EU Startup Nations Standards of Excellence declaration.

The ESNA Forum served as a unique platform for members to actively reaffirm their commitment to advancing eight essential standards crucial for the prosperous future of European startups. These standards encompass fast startup creation, smooth market entry, attracting and retaining talents, stock options, innovation in regulation and procurement, access to finance, social inclusion, diversity, protecting democratic values, and embracing a digital-first approach.

The ESNA Forum facilitated the exchange of best practices, the development of policy-making tools and initiatives, and the cultivation of a robust startup ecosystem across member countries. ESNA's Executive Director emphasised the organisation's dedication to supporting countries in creating favourable conditions for startup growth throughout their life cycle, noting that the ESNA Forum is a collaborative platform to achieve collective goals.

The Executive Director expressed ESNA's pride in contributing to the Spanish Presidency's efforts to advance the startup agenda by acknowledging Spain's leadership in the Council of the EU and its vision for a united and forward-thinking Europe. The ESNA Forum discussions centred on uplifting Europe's startup ecosystem, with the belief that the outcomes would serve as a strong foundation for the continuity of ESNA's mission and shared vision, inspiring a future of innovation and growth. The event exemplified a commitment to fostering collaboration, innovation, and sustained growth within the European startup landscape.

Figure 1 ESNA Forum 2023, León

2. Background and Objectives

This report, which corresponds to Deliverable 6.3 within Work Package 6 of the ESNA project, aims to comprehensively present the ESNA Forum 2023 outcomes.

The ESNA Forum, as a face-to-face meeting of ministers and member countries, is ESNA's highest-level event and serves as the primary annual platform to bring forward a political startup agenda, for providing updated ESNA's status reports and presenting milestones for the coming year. This outcome aligns with ESNA Objective O.6.3: to organise a final high-level conference to present and discuss the project's results.

The ESNA Forum was structured into two distinct parts. The first part included high-level updates, which all participants participated in. The second part was reserved for ESNA members only and provided an opportunity for in-depth exploration of specific topics.

The main objectives of the ESNA Forum 2023 were to learn about the latest government views on startup ecosystems in different countries.

The ESNA Forum, as a platform for learning and sharing, served as a unique opportunity to gain insights into the different perspectives of participating countries regarding their governmental views on fostering and sustaining startup ecosystems. This exchange of knowledge and ideas, integral to the ESNA Forum, ensured that all participants were well-informed and engaged in the discussions.

Current state of the Alliance with milestones achieved during the year

An integral component was the presentation of the "State of the Alliance," which highlighted the milestones and achievements achieved throughout the year.

Goals set for 2024

Setting the course for the future, the ESNA Forum presented the strategic goals and milestones ESNA aims to achieve in the coming year, contributing to the continuous evolution of European startup ecosystems.

Increasing the visibility of ESNA's work through the conference

With a dual focus on transparency and outreach, the ESNA Forum sought to increase the visibility of ESNA's impactful work by engaging in constructive dialogue, sharing insights, and fostering collaboration.

This report delves into the nuanced discussions, key takeaways and strategic insights that emerged from the ESNA Forum. It provides a detailed account of the high-level conference's pivotal role in advancing ESNA's overarching goals.

3. Agenda and Sessions

ESNA Forum 2023 Agenda – 19th of October 2023

Morning Session:

09:00 – 09:30: Arrivals and accreditation

09:30 – 09:45: Opening of ESNA Forum - Welcome addresses and opening speeches from the Spanish Secretary of State for Digital and Artificial Intelligence (SEDIA); DG INCIBE; ESNA

09:45 – 10:00: State of the Alliance (ESNA)

10:00 – 10:30: Declaration of Intent on Tech Entrepreneurship – “An EU approach to Startups and Scaleups” (Spanish Govt.)

10:30 – 11:30: Roundtable on the Declaration of Intent

11:30 – 11:35: Speech by the European Commission

11:35 – 11:40: Closing of Morning Session (Hosting Country & ESNA)

11:40 – 11:55: Family Photo

11:55 – 13:30: Lunch Break

Afternoon Session:

13:30 – 14:30: Interactive Working Session (ESNA Team, ESNA Members)

13:30 – 14:45: ENISE Conference & INCIBE - Topics: highlights on entrepreneurship efforts in cybersecurity (Governmental Level)

14:30 – 15:20: Deep Dive in ESNA projects - Introduction, SNS Standards, Data Platform, Tech Talent + Real-time interactive feedback (ESNA Team)

15:20 – 15:35: Coffee Break

15:35 – 16:05: Digital Services Act (DSA) and the Digital Market Act (DMA) (Commission)

16:05 – 16:15: Spain as an Entrepreneurial Nation (SG for Digital Talent and Entrepreneurship)

16:15 – 16:25: INCIBE Cybersecurity and Entrepreneurship (INCIBE)

16:25 – 16:45: Results from Interactive Feedback & Closing Remarks (ESNA Team)

4. Key Themes and Discussions

Morning Session Highlights:

- Presentations by SEDIA, DG INCIBE, and ESNA on the achievements to date and future goals.
- Declaration of Intent on Tech Entrepreneurship: The Spanish government will give a detailed presentation, followed by a roundtable discussion with representatives of Member States to deliberate on the declaration's implications.
- Speech by the European Commission: A brief address focusing on the Commission's support and strategic alignment with ESNA's goals.

Afternoon Session Highlights:

- Interactive Working Session: ESNA members engaged in collaborative discussions to explore specific topics, including SNS standards, data platforms, and tech talent initiatives.
- Digital Services Act (DSA) and Digital Market Act (DMA): A presentation by the Commission on these critical legislative frameworks and their impact on tech entrepreneurship.
- INCIBE Cybersecurity and Entrepreneurship: Discussions on the integration of cybersecurity in entrepreneurship, including on-site visits and success stories from INCIBE's programs.
- Spain as an Entrepreneurial Nation: Insights from the SG for Digital Talent and Entrepreneurship on Spain's initiatives and vision for fostering a robust entrepreneurial ecosystem.

5. Decisions and Resolutions

The ESNA Forum 2023 witnessed Spain's signing of a major commitment, which held the European Council presidency. The commitment highlighted the pivotal role of startups and scaleups in Europe's future economy and society. The Declaration was a central theme, focusing on enhancing the startup ecosystem across Europe through strategic initiatives, legal harmonization, and cross-regional collaboration, which is reproduced in full here below:

The declaration is available on the website of the Spanish Presidency of the EU Council: <https://spanish-presidency.consilium.europa.eu/media/ycnoemfo/an-eu-approach-to-startups-and-scaleups.pdf>

It is reproduced integrally below:

AN EU APPROACH TO STARTUPS AND SCALEUPS

Startups and scaleups are key to Europe's future economy and society, as highlighted by the Digital Decade Policy Programme adopted in December 2022.

Among the digital targets established, it highlighted the growth of innovative scaleups and the improvement of their access to finance with the objective to at least double the number of unicorns in the EU by 2030 and ensuring more than 90% of SMEs reach at least a basic level of digital intensity by the end of this decade. In 2021, 26 EU Member States signed the Europe Startup Nations Standards Declaration, committing to take action at a national level to meet 8 standards of the Declaration and ensure they offer growth-friendly conditions for startups. Furthermore, another outcome of the declaration was the establishment of the Europe Startup Nations Alliance (ESNA) to support Member States in achieving these goals. All of this demonstrates strong recognition of the importance of startups and scaleups in boosting EU's productivity, creating jobs and ensuring innovation enters the market to help improve people's lives. Supporting startups and scaleups is also an important way to achieve the targets of the EU Green Deal and the UN Sustainable Development Goals.

The European Union offers a significant opportunity to startups, with figures like a GDP per capita of 37,000 EUR and a consumer base of 450 million individuals⁴. Furthermore, its Member States are underpinned with sophisticated digital infrastructures and the highest percentage contribution of e-commerce to GDP. Additionally, the European Union commands the global innovation index, with five of its Member States securing a rank within the top 10.

The new institutional mandate starting in 2024 offers a window of opportunity for the European Union to put forward a genuinely European, comprehensive and cohesive EU Startups and Scaleups Strategy to foster the EU single market. Start-ups and scaleups are crucial for the economy, competitiveness of the EU and contribute to the technological leadership of Europe. These highly innovative companies are key to providing solutions to global challenges. In this sense, the signatory parties strongly recommend the following:

- **Ensure the centralised coordination of the EU Startups and Scaleups Strategy within the Commission.** Acknowledging that startup-relevant measures are the responsibility of multiple Directorates General, the Strategy would cover initiatives targeting all stages of a startup's lifecycle, from creation and growth to exit strategies, building upon initiatives such as the EU Startup Nations Standards and the European Innovation Council.

- **Promote discussions to create an overall EU framework in support of EU startups and scaleups.** It should include common definitions, to enhance the EU's global competitiveness, and work towards the improvement of an internal, homogeneous and border-free market where startups can thrive and benefit from economies of scale.

- **Support the establishment and development of non-binding regulatory sandboxes across the EU, including the cross-border ones, to assist entrepreneurs in navigating digital legislation and fostering innovation.** Setting up of sandboxes for discovering innovation opportunities emanating from existing legislation and for helping compliance with it should be further promoted. This is an important opportunity for our startups to assess the upcoming tech regulation.

- **Implement ties with start-up ecosystems of other regions in the world.** In particular, in the context of the European Union – Latin American and Caribbean (LAC) Digital Alliance, it is now the time to promote collaboration across both regions and explore synergies, building on the Accelerators of the Alliance and making use of the Global Gateway funds.

Although women make up half of the EU's population, female-owned startups and scaleups are still rare, accounting for only 11% of founders in the EU6. The IMF estimates that closing the credit gap for women-owned and women-led SMEs would result in a 12 percent increase in annual incomes on average by 2030⁷. The signatory parties agree on the importance of the potential in the EU Tech Entrepreneur Strategy to address the gender gap, regarding:

- 1) Avoiding unconscious bias in access to finance and identifying and sharing good practice, by for example reviewing EU forms and application processes.
- 2) Exploring policy-options for introducing incentives to promote gender balance in startups and scaleups.

While there have been notable improvements, financing remains a challenge for entrepreneurs. Venture capital has grown to 49 billion EUR, but it lags behind the USA at 233 billion EUR and China at 58 billion EUR. In this regard, the EU accounts for 249 unicorns at the end of 2022, while the USA has 1,503, China for 348 and India for 108 of which more than half born over the last two years.

To address our joint financing challenges, Member States signatories agree that the EU Startups and Scaleups Strategy should take into account the financing challenges. Strengthening the Capital Markets Union will be instrumental to maximize the contribution of private funding to EU startups and scaleups. Initiatives such as the European Tech Champions Initiative (ETCI) could be strengthened by various means, while other solutions could be discussed such as the possibility to synergies and cross-border collaboration between national venture capital funds targeting scaleups in growth stages.

ESNA is an important forum in ensuring that Member States advance in implementing best practice policies for startups and scaleups under national competencies. Having in mind the Data Platform and the One-Stop-Shop Talent Service Desk that ESNA is developing, it is then important that ESNA becomes an EDIC.

In closing, the signatory parties commit to driving innovation, fostering collaboration, and catalysing positive change in the startups and scaleups ecosystem. Together, the European Union and the Member States embark on a journey to shape the future of technology, creating opportunities, and ensuring a sustainable and thriving digital

landscape. We firmly believe that start-ups, with their innovative and digital technologies, are crucial for the future competitiveness of the EU and are key in addressing global crises. The signatory parties agree to turning this vision into reality, forging a brighter and more interconnected tech-enabled world for all.

All EU Member States and European Economic Area countries are invited to join this declaration. Additional signatories may adhere at any time.

6. Stakeholders Contribution

The ESNA Forum 2023 brought together diverse stakeholders, including government representatives from member states, European Commission officials, and ESNA associate members. The contributions from these stakeholders were pivotal in shaping the discussions and outcomes of the forum. Key contributions included:

Government Representatives:

- Austria
- Belgium
- Bulgaria
- Germany
- Ireland
- Luxembourg
- Malta
- The Netherlands
- Spain

European Commission Representatives:

A representative from DG CNCT delivered a speech focusing on the Commission's support for ESNA's initiatives and their alignment with broader European policies and strategies, including the Digital Services Act (DSA) and the Digital Market Act (DMA).

ESNA Members:

ESNA Members represented their respective organisations in the interactive working sessions, contributing valuable feedback and suggestions on ESNA projects, including SNS standards, data platforms, and tech talent initiatives. They represented the following countries:

- Belgium
- Czech Republic
- Estonia
- France
- Ireland
- Lithuania
- The Netherlands

These contributions from diverse stakeholders enriched the discussions, ensuring a holistic approach to advancing the European startup ecosystem. The participants' collaborative spirit and shared vision were evident in the resolutions and actionable items agreed upon during the forum.

7. Impact Assessment

The ESNA Forum 2023 materialised a significant commitment in the form of the Declaration of Intent on Tech Entrepreneurship, signed under the Spanish Presidency of the Council of the EU. This declaration outlines several strategic initiatives aimed at bolstering the European startup ecosystem. The main points of the declaration include:

- Assigning responsibility for an EU Tech Entrepreneurship Strategy to a lead Commissioner and a single Directorate General.
- Establishing new regulatory sandboxes to assist entrepreneurs in navigating digital legislation.
- Addressing gender disparities through bias-free financing processes, incentives for gender-balanced companies, and mentoring programs for women.
- Enhancing access to finance through European Digital Bonds, a pan-European fund for early-stage startups, and a unique insurance program for innovation.

While the full impact of this declaration will unfold over time, the ESNA Forum 2023 achieved an immediate impact by bringing together representatives from 15 member states.

The ESNA Forum served as a critical platform for sharing best practices among member states and creating valuable connections between key policy influencers at the national level. It helped align national policies with the SNS's overarching goals by facilitating open dialogue and collaboration. This alignment is expected to foster a more supportive and dynamic environment for European startups, enhancing global competitiveness.

Discussions also allowed member states to learn from each other's successes and challenges, promoting a collective approach to overcoming common obstacles in the startup ecosystem. This unity and shared vision among member states are instrumental in driving forward the ambitious goals set out in the Declaration of Intent and ensuring sustained growth and innovation within the European startup landscape.

8. Challenges and Opportunities

The ESNA Forum highlighted several challenges and opportunities within the European startup ecosystem. The forum's discussions and presentations identified critical areas for improvement and potential strategies for addressing these challenges.

A. Challenges:

Access to Finance:

Despite growth in venture capital, Europe still needs to catch up with the USA and China regarding funding availability for startups. The limited access to substantial financing remains a significant barrier for entrepreneurs.

Proposed Strategy: Develop European Digital Bonds and a pan-European fund for early-stage startups to direct more capital towards tech ventures, a move that holds great promise for the future of European startups.

Regulatory Fragmentation:

The varying legal and regulatory frameworks across EU member states pose challenges for startups aiming to scale across borders. Inconsistent regulations can hinder growth and market entry.

Proposed Strategy: Legal harmonisation through minimal regulatory alignment and establishing regulatory sandboxes to assist startups in navigating complex digital legislation.

Gender Gap in Entrepreneurship:

Female representation among startup founders is low, with women accounting for only 11% of founders in the EU. Addressing gender disparity is crucial for a more inclusive ecosystem.

Proposed Strategy: Implement bias-free financing processes, gender-balanced incentives, and mentoring programs to support female entrepreneurs.

Tech Talent Scarcity:

The need for more skilled tech professionals continues to be a bottleneck for startups seeking to innovate and expand. Attracting and retaining talent is a critical challenge.

Proposed Strategy: Development of the One-Stop-Shop Talent Service Desk and personalised help guides to facilitate talent acquisition and mobility across member states.

B. Opportunities

Unified Market for Startups:

By creating a homogeneous and border-free market, the EU can enhance its global competitiveness, providing startups with a more extensive customer base and economies of scale.

Proposed Strategy: Commitment to minimal legal harmonisation and implementing common definitions and standards to streamline market entry and operations.

Expansion of ESNA's Role:

Increasing the financing and scope of ESNA will support more initiatives, fostering a robust startup ecosystem across Europe.

Proposed Strategy: Secure additional funding for ESNA, invite EU candidate countries to join, and expand the advisory and support services offered to member states.

The ESNA Forum 2023 effectively identified these challenges and opportunities, setting the stage for actionable strategies that can drive meaningful progress in Europe's startup ecosystem.

9. Next Steps and Follow-Up Actions

The ESNA Forum 2023 materialised a significant commitment in the form of the Declaration of Intent on Tech Entrepreneurship, signed under the Spanish Presidency of the Council of the EU. This declaration outlines several strategic initiatives aimed at bolstering the European startup ecosystem. The main points of the declaration include:

Building Momentum for the Next ESNA Forum 2024:

To maintain momentum for the next ESNA Forum in 2024 and continue advancing the startup agenda, active communication and engagement with stakeholders, including government representatives, ESNA members, industry experts, and policymakers, will be crucial. This will be achieved through regular updates, consultations, and feedback sessions, along with the establishment of a dedicated communication channel for stakeholders to share their views and suggestions.

Encouraging collaboration among member states to share best practices and successful strategies in implementing the Startup Nations Standards (SNS) and other initiatives discussed at the forum will also be a priority. To facilitate knowledge exchange, follow-up workshops, webinars, and meetings will be organized, ensuring the ongoing dissemination of best practices among member states.

Enhancing ESNA's role and resources involves expanding membership by extending invitations to other EU candidate countries to join ESNA. This will promote a more inclusive and expansive startup ecosystem, fostering greater collaboration and support for startups across Europe.

Strengthening the Network of Focal Points

To further advance the startup agenda, workshops will be organized for Focal Points to facilitate knowledge exchange and collaborative activities. These workshops aim to build a more robust network of national representatives dedicated to advancing the startup agenda.

In preparation for the next ESNA Forum, collaboration with Brussels, the next country to adhere to the SNS Declaration and hold the Presidency of the European Union Council, will be essential. This event will build on the outcomes of the 2023 forum, continuing the dialogue and collaboration among member states to advance the European startup agenda.

These follow-up actions, all in line with our unwavering commitment to the resolutions and commitments made during the ESNA Forum 2023, are designed to ensure their effective implementation. By focusing on collaboration, inclusivity, and innovation, ESNA aims to drive significant progress in creating a supportive environment for startups across Europe, ultimately positioning Europe as a global leader in tech entrepreneurship.

10. Conclusion

The ESNA Forum 2023 played a pivotal role in advancing the startup agenda and solidifying Europe's position in entrepreneurship leadership. The forum's outcomes align closely with ESNA's mission to create a supportive and dynamic ecosystem for startups across Europe. The critical impacts anticipated from the ESNA Forum include in a nutshell:

Strategic Leadership and Coordination

By adopting a cohesive EU Startup ecosystem Strategy, the ESNA Forum sets the stage for coordinated efforts across member states, ensuring that policies and initiatives are aligned to support startups at every stage of their lifecycle.

Enhanced Global Competitiveness

The commitment to legal harmonisation and establishing regulatory sandboxes will create a more unified and competitive market for European startups. This move is expected to attract more investment and talent to the region, positioning Europe as a prime destination for entrepreneurial activity.

By delivering on these strategic fronts, the ESNA Forum 2023 has set a strong foundation for the continued advancement of the startup agenda in Europe. The ESNA Forum's outcomes will drive significant progress toward making Europe a global leader in entrepreneurship, fostering innovation, and creating sustainable economic growth.

ANNEX: EVENT PICTURES

[A short video of the event is available here.](#)

